

could be governed by means of a pendulum, it would be of extreme use in making machines rise or fall or for stability purposes. If they were moved slightly up or down, the pendulum would at once alter the gear and so bring the planes into different operation. He thought it would be very important if it could be managed in a proper manner. We are not altogether successful with the amount of thrust we get at the screw, and he should like to know if Mr. Hawkins had any experience with the propeller and if he could give them any idea of the approximate thrust.

Mr. LEES said he should like to ask whether any experiment had been tried with a model made on the plan shown? It seemed to him the method of using a pendulum was a very suitable one, and one which might actually be used with a gliding apparatus. The gliding apparatus used at the St. Louis Exhibition was balanced by a pendulum, the pendulum being Mr. Burrough's body. Therefore, if a pendulum could be used, it would certainly help us to overcome the effort of coming down, and do it safely. If we cannot manage to balance the machine in some way or other, he was afraid we might get a machine that will lift itself, but it will never be a practical one. He hoped the author would continue his experiments and test them on a model, so that one could see whether it will work or not.

In reply to a question as to whether any details could now be given as to the construction of the model that is governed gyroscopically,

Mr. HAWKINS said: I have made some experiments with gliding models—in fact, I have made several of them with fixed plain gliders of different types—and I got very satisfactory gliders in calm air or inside a barn. But when I tried them in the open air without choosing my day and time, I found them smash up after the second or third time very often. They would not come down straight; they would get tilted up and have a big drop, and very often the drop occurred when they were near the ground. With regard to the governed glider—of course, pendulum-governed—if the pendulum be analysed, it will be seen it is merely an *aéroplane* held to the wind by a weight. It is much the same as a weight below the centre of effort, only the weight is to be in a position where it has a certain amount of mechanical advantage. With regard to the glider model, I do not

want to say too much at present. I have only made one actual good model, and that is smashed up now. I am afraid I tried it rather beyond its endurance. The model was rather a rough one. Since then I have decided to build a succession of models, and hope to arrive at some data worth having. One can easily see that this type is a complicated idea, but one must remember that the ordinary *aéroplane* is designed for two purposes—lift and stability. This has five features—lift, stability, quick acceleration, automatic retardation, and, fifthly, it should become a glider automatically if the motor stops. That might not be important for anyone but the person in the thing. Also I lighten it to take a corner with the outer wing up, and so avoid any great loss of energy in turning—in fact, it appears to me a pendulum-governed machine acts almost exactly in the way a bird does. In quietly flying it does, especially in turning. About the models I have made of the fan, I have made several, but they have been fairly rough—in fact, the first used up more of its energy in turning than it did on the air. The latter ones have shown a great deal of increasing efficiency, and, of course, it is very easy to work out what the efficiency might be if there were no power used up in turning the ends. Referring to the diagram, when they are made like this, with two bearings supporting a working surface, when any work comes on this surface the result is a tremendous turn in each of these two ends. I found that happened in my machines, and it means a tremendous waste of power. Another tremendous loss is in the turning movement of the fans. You do not get the fans getting their ideal motion. I think my work up to the present, allowing for a certain amount of friction and that sort of thing, shows there ought to be in practice a thrust of something like 67 or 68 lbs. per horse-power. Of course, that is enormous compared with the screw.

Notes on an Aluminium Kite.

BY ALAN H. BURGOYNE.

I have made many kites subsequently, and of many different forms, but always came back to that represented in the photographs before the meeting. It resembles in some particulars that of Mr. Cody, though I had made it long before I had seen or heard of Mr. Cody's kite. The essential

difference is in the wings, where I do away with the eccentric protuberances which he favours. One particular feature I would point out is my employment of steel springs to fly the kite from at the kite-end of the connections. Mr. Cody employs all his springs at the winder end, but I find the double use of springs renders the flight of the kite infinitely more steady.

My aluminium kite was of the following dimensions:—

	Ft.	Ins.
Extreme breadth from tip of wing to tip of wing	12	8
Extreme length	10	9
(Of which the tail took up)	4	0
Wings, width	3	0
„ length.	6	0
Tail, width	6	0
„ length	4	0

The aluminium I bought in hollow rods of from $\frac{1}{4}$ in. to $\frac{5}{8}$ in. in thickness. The sides of the three "boxes" were made of eight rods, 6 ft. long and $\frac{1}{4}$ in. thickness. The wing supports were of one $\frac{5}{8}$ in. rod, 12 ft. 3 ins. in length, passing right across the kite and secured by lashings to each "box" in turn. The tube, fore and aft, was also of $\frac{5}{8}$ in., and was wired with strain-eye attachments to all eight box rods. In fact, the strain was distributed evenly from the tips of the wing-rod to the tips of the fore and aft rod, making a tightly-braced quadrilateral.

Two 3 ft. tubes of $\frac{3}{8}$ in. were used as vertical supports, and in the bottoms of these I placed two small wheels, so that the transport of the kite when set up was greatly facilitated.

The tension on the linen was made, not by the usual cross-bracing, but by means of aluminium rods running across each end of the boxes both top and bottom. This system made the kite not only perfectly rigid, but also more easy to take to pieces. The fastenings for these were round brass sockets, set cross-ways. I have taken the kite to pieces and set it up again in under half an hour.

The linen is ordinary shirt-front linen of the finest quality—indeed, it was the most expensive item, for I required a dense texture with a minimum of weight.

The cord I use is "cod-cord," the first 1500 feet being light, and the remainder (12,500 feet in all) of similar type, but much stouter. To relieve the strain as much as possible I had a steel-spring,

6 inches in length, fixed at every attachment, and further had three or four more (according to weather) between the two flying rings. As regards weight, the kite was a marvel of lightness, weighing exactly $12\frac{3}{4}$ lbs., without springs, of course. The reel and methods of control were, and are still, very primitive, since I have devoted all my attention to the kites. To ease the pull on the reel (a large bore reel with clutches), I devised an elastic tension pulley, using an india-rubber door closer, an inch thick, and several pulleys with steel springs.

My highest flight attained is between 10,000 and 12,000 ft. I dare not guess nearer, as I could only calculate by the amount of cord out, and the angle of the the kite. That was with a small ten-foot kite.

The PRESIDENT: It now only devolves upon me to ask you to record your thanks to the readers of the several very valuable papers, which I am sure have been highly appreciated.

Mr. FROST: It is my pleasant duty to propose a vote of thanks to the President, and to thank him for so kindly and generously offering a prize for the best flying model, under certain conditions and considerations. Our best thanks are due to him, and I hope much energy will be put forth to obtain that prize.

Colonel FULLERTON: I beg to second that.

The vote of thanks was carried by acclamation.

Applications for Patents.

(Made in January, February, and March, 1905.)

The following list of Applications for Patents connected with Aëronautics has been specially compiled for the AËRONAUTICAL JOURNAL by Messrs. BROMHEAD & Co., Patent Agents, 33, Cannon Street, London, E.C.

1084. January 19th. JOSE WEISS. Improvements relating to Flying Machines.

1140. January 20th. ANDRE GAMBIN. Improvements in Propellers for Marine and Aerial Navigation. (Date applied for under Patent Acts, 1901. 3rd February, 1904, being date of application in France.)